

CREEP OPTIMIZATION OF ARALL®-4 LAMINATES¹

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ABSTRACT

The paper addresses the creep response of ARALL®-4 laminates at 121° C and the means of optimizing the extent of creep by prestraining. Experimental data generated from tensile and creep characterization tests on the material constituents of ARALL-4 are employed as input to an analytical model developed to simulate the time-dependent response of this hybrid composite. The analytical predictions are correlated with the results of creep experiments on ARALL-4 laminates with different prestrain histories. It is demonstrated both experimentally and analytically that mechanical prestraining of ARALL-4 can substantially reduce the magnitude of creep strains in this material. The demonstrated predictive capability of the analytical model provides the manufacturer with a tool for optimizing the creep response of ARALL-4 for the given application.

INTRODUCTION

ARALL-4 is a recently introduced hybrid composite belonging to a family of laminates called ARALL developed at the Delft University of Technology in the Netherlands¹ and currently marketed by Alcoa. These laminates consist of thin layers of aramid/epoxy prepreg sandwiched between aluminum sheets and are characterized by good damage tolerance and high fatigue crack growth resistance^{2,3}.

The first variants of ARALL, ARALL 1-3 laminates, have been developed for applications with generally small temperature excursions from ambient conditions⁴. These laminates use a 120° C cure resin prepreg with a maximum recommended service temperature of 90° C. Under these conditions, the creep effects in the individual layers are not considered to be significant. ARALL-4 on the other hand was developed specifically for elevated temperature environments. It is made with aluminum alloy 2024-T8 sheets and aramid/epoxy prepreg (50/50 fiber-resin weight ratio) fabricated by the 3M Company. The nominal thickness of the aluminum sheets is 0.3 mm and the prepreg nominal thickness is 0.2 mm. The epoxy resin employed in the aramid/epoxy prepreg is a high temperature 3M AF 191 adhesive bond film (175° C cure temperature). The maximum operating temperature for this family of ARALL laminates is thus 160° C. In this temperature range, the time-dependent response of both the aluminum and aramid/epoxy constituents may play an important role in controlling the overall response of these hybrid laminates.

Previous investigation⁵ addressed the creep response of ARALL-4 laminates and its constituents at 121° C. It was demonstrated that ARALL-4 exhibits substantial creep effects at stress levels in the vicinity of the proportional limit determined from a quasi-static tensile test. The creep response is a nonlinear function of time and the applied stress level and is primarily due to the creep characteristics of the aluminum layers. Using an analytical model developed to predict the time-dependent response of ARALL-4, it was also demonstrated that the magnitude of creep depends on both the applied stress and the state of residual stress in aluminum and aramid/epoxy layers. This offers the possibility of minimizing creep effects by altering the state of residual stress with mechanical prestraining of ARALL-4 above the yield stress.

This paper outlines the results of an investigation to develop a methodology of optimizing the creep response of ARALL-4 by mechanical prestraining. The previously developed analytical model is extended to enable calculation of the magnitude of residual stresses in the aluminum and aramid/epoxy layers as a function of the prestrain stress level. The predicted creep response of ARALL-4 with an altered residual stress due to prestraining is compared with

¹ARALL is a trademark of Alcoa.

available experimental creep data obtained from a specimen with the same prestrain history. The model is subsequently employed to determine the prestrain stress level that minimizes creep effects for the considered example.

SUMMARY OF PREVIOUS INVESTIGATION

In order to set the results of present investigation in perspective, selected results of the time-dependent response of ARALL-4 at 121° C outlined by Pindera et al⁵ are presented in the sequel.

The stress-strain response of a typical ARALL-4 laminate tested along the fiber direction at a strain rate of 1%/min is given in Fig. 1. Included in the figure are the stress-strain curves of the aluminum and aramid/epoxy constituents tested under identical conditions. The response characteristics of ARALL-4 and its constituents are summarized in Table 1 in terms of elastic and inelastic material parameters.

Table 1. Material parameters of ARALL-4 and its constituents at 121° C

Material	E_l (GPa)	E_T (GPa)	ν_l	σ_f^{pl} (MPa)
ARALL-4 Laminate	59.1	--	0.345	303
2024-T8 Aluminum	70.3	70.3	0.340	331
Aramid/Epoxy	46.7	2.98	0.400	--

The creep response of ARALL-4 laminates tested for 8 hours at five different stress levels is presented in Fig. 2. The five stress levels were 207, 241, 276, 310 and 345 MPa. Three of the stress levels were well within the linear range of the stress-strain response of the tested laminates, and the remaining two were at, and slightly above, the proportional limit. Figure 2 illustrates that the creep response of ARALL-4 is negligible below a certain critical stress and increases in a nonlinear fashion with applied stress. This threshold value is in the vicinity of 207 MPa which is substantially lower than the proportional limit obtained from the constant strain rate tests presented in Fig. 1. In the vicinity of the proportional limit the extent of creep becomes quite pronounced.

Fig. 1 Stress-strain response of ARALL-4 and its constituents at 121° C ($\dot{\epsilon} = 1\%/min$).

Fig. 2 Creep response of ARALL-4 at 121° C tested at five stress levels.

Figure 3 illustrates the creep response of aluminum alloy 2024-T8 tested under the same conditions as the ARALL-4 laminate. The substantially nonlinear, stress-dependent creep of aluminum is similar to the creep response observed in ARALL-4 laminates. The creep of aramid/epoxy loaded in the fiber direction is illustrated in Fig. 4. The small extent of creep observed in the case of aramid/epoxy suggests that the aluminum layers play the dominant role in the overall time-dependent response of this hybrid composite.

Fig. 3 Creep response of aluminum alloy 2024-T8 at five stress levels.

Fig. 4 Creep response of aramid/epoxy 0° coupons at three stress levels.

ANALYTICAL MODEL FOR ARALL-4 LAMINATES

The lamination⁶ theory is employed in the present investigation to develop an analytical model for the quasi-static and creep response of ARALL-4 laminates on the basis of the known response of the constituent layers. The aluminum layers are taken to be isotropic and elasto-visco-plastic with the following constitutive equations :

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{ij} = S_{ijkl}^e \dot{\sigma}_{kl} + S_{ijkl}^{vp} \dot{\sigma}_{kl} + m_{ij} \frac{m_{kl} \dot{\sigma}_{kl}}{h} + \alpha_{ij} \dot{T} \quad (1)$$

where S_{ijkl}^e and S_{ijkl}^{vp} are the instantaneous elastic and viscoplastic compliance tensors, m_{ij} is the normal vector to the yield surface (in this case von Mises) and h is the hardening function proportional to the tangent modulus in the elastoplastic region. For the aluminum alloy employed in ARALL-4, S_{ijkl}^{vp} of the following form models the response under plane stress loading with sufficient accuracy :

$$\underline{S}^{vp} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -\nu \\ -\nu & 1 \end{bmatrix} g(\sigma^{eff}) n(\sigma^{eff}) t^{n(\sigma^{eff})-1}$$

The functions g and n are given in terms of the effective stress σ^{eff} :

$$n = n_0 + n_1 \sigma^{eff}$$

$$g = g_0 + g_1 \sigma^{eff} \quad \text{for } 207 \text{ MPa} \leq \sigma^{eff} \leq 310 \text{ MPa}$$

$$g = g'_0 + g'_1 \sigma^{eff} \quad \text{for } 310 \text{ MPa} \leq \sigma^{eff} \leq 345 \text{ MPa}$$

where

$$\sigma^{eff} = \sqrt{\sigma_{11}^2 - \sigma_{11}\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{22}^2}$$

and the constants n_0 , n_1 , g_0 , g_1 , g'_0 and g'_1 are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Viscoelastic parameters of aluminum alloy 2024-T8 at 121° C

n_0	n_1 (1/GPa)	g_0 (1/GPa-hr)	g_1 (1/GPa ² -hr)	g'_0 (1/GPa-hr)	g'_1 (1/GPa ² -hr)
-0.0625	1.414	-0.1232	0.799	-1.298	4.58

The aramid/epoxy layers are taken to be transversely isotropic and linearly viscoelastic with the following constitutive equations :

$$\epsilon_{ij} = \int_0^t S_{ijkl}(t-\tau) \frac{\partial \sigma_{kl}}{\partial \tau} d\tau + \alpha_{ij} \Delta T \quad (2)$$

The experimentally observed creep response of aramid/epoxy suggests a four-parameter representation of the creep compliance functions $S_{1111}(t)$, $S_{1212}(t)$ and $S_{2222}(t)$ which are sufficient to model the response under plane stress loading :

$$S_{1111}(t) = \frac{1}{E_{10}} + \frac{1}{E_{11}} (1 - e^{-\lambda_{11}t}) + \mu_{10}t$$

$$S_{1212}(t) = -\nu_{12} S_{1111}(t) \quad \text{since} \quad \nu_{12}(t) = \text{constant}$$

$$S_{2222}(t) = \frac{1}{E_{20}} + \frac{1}{E_{22}} (1 - e^{-\lambda_{22}t}) + \mu_{20}t$$

The parameters E_{11} , λ_{11} , μ_{10} and E_{22} , λ_{22} , μ_{20} are given in Table 3 (the elastic parameters E_{10} , E_{20} and ν_{12} are given in Table 1).

Table 3. Viscoelastic creep compliance parameters of aramid/epoxy at 121° C

E_{11} (GPa)	λ_{11} (1/hr)	μ_{10} (1/GPa-hr)	E_{22} (GPa)	λ_{22} (1/hr)	μ_{20} (1/GPa-hr)
884.0	2.137	6.09×10^{-5}	4.47	4.713	2.78×10^{-2}

Applying the assumptions of the lamination theory to the incremental form of the constitutive equations given by Eqs. 1 and 2 leads to the following relation between the inplane laminate strain increments, $d\epsilon$, mechanically and thermally applied force resultant increments, dN and dN^T respectively, and past history :

$$d\epsilon = A^{-1}(t, t+\Delta t) \{dN + dN^T + dH\} \quad (3)$$

where $A(t, t+\Delta t)$ is the instantaneous laminate extensional stiffness matrix and the effect of past history is included in the vector dH . In order to determine the quasi-static or creep response of ARALL-4, the above equations have to be integrated incrementally starting from some initial (known) state of laminate strains and stresses.

CREEP OPTIMIZATION BY PRESTRAINING

The analytical model outlined in the preceding section is first employed to predict the creep response of ARALL-4 for two loading histories. In the first instance, a stress of 310 MPa and a temperature change of -56° C were applied in an instantaneous manner to model the creep response of ARALL-4 at 121° C. The temperature change of -56° C was employed to estimate the state of residual stress induced during cool-down from the cure temperature of 177° C to the test temperature. For the second loading history, the temperature change of -56° C was followed by mechanical prestraining to the stress level of 414 MPa and subsequent unloading. Next, the laminate was loaded in an instantaneous manner to 310 MPa and the creep response determined.

Figure 5 illustrates the comparison between predictions of the analytical model and experimental data for mechanical prestraining to 414 MPa. The initial state of longitudinal residual stress in the aluminum and aramid/epoxy layers due to the applied temperature change predicted by the model was 18.7 MPa and -39.5 MPa, respectively. The prestraining cycle changed the longitudinal residual stresses in the aluminum and aramid/epoxy layers to -57.4 MPa and 121.6 MPa, respectively.

The predicted creep response of ARALL-4 at 310 MPa before and after mechanical prestraining is illustrated in Fig. 6. The experimental data obtained under the same loading conditions is included in the figure. Evidently, the correlation between analysis and experiment is good for the outlined loading conditions. The small differences between analysis and experiment are primarily due to the differences in the instantaneous response predicted and observed experimentally. These differences can be eliminated by adjusting the magnitude of the instantaneous compliance predicted by the model. The experimental and analytical evidence presented in Fig. 6 illustrates that the reduction in the creep response due to prestraining under the outlined conditions is substantial.

Fig. 5 Pretraining of ARALL-4 to 414 MPa - analysis and experiment.

Fig. 6 Creep response of ARALL-4 before and after prestraining to 414 MPa.

Fig. 7 Creep strain of ARALL-4 after 8 hrs as a function of prestrain load.

Fig. 8 Residual stresses in the constituent layers as a function of prestrain load.

The demonstrated predictive capability of the developed analytical model justifies the use of the model in optimizing the prestraining procedure in order to minimize creep effects. The results of such optimization for the creep response of ARALL-4 subjected to the applied stress of 310 MPa are presented in Fig. 7 where the magnitude of creep strain after 8 hours is given as a function of prestrain history. These results indicate that the magnitude of creep first decreases in a monotonic manner with increasing prestrain stress until it reaches a minimum at approximately 500 MPa, and then increases slightly. The slight increase is probably due to the creep of the aramid/epoxy layers which become subjected to increasingly higher tensile stresses with increasing prestrain loads. The changes in the longitudinal residual stresses in the aluminum and aramid/epoxy layers caused by prestraining are presented in Fig. 8. These changes, in conjunction with the observed creep response of the constituents given in Figs. 3 and 4, help to understand the physical mechanism which leads to the reduction in the creep response of ARALL-4.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this investigation indicate that it is possible to reduce the extent of creep observed in ARALL-4 laminates at 121° C by mechanical prestraining. Creep of ARALL-4 at this temperature is primarily due to the creep characteristics of the aluminum layers which are nonlinear functions of both the applied stress and time. Mechanical prestraining past the yield point alters the residual state of stress in the aluminum and aramid/epoxy layers. In particular, prestraining ARALL-4 in tension changes the longitudinal residual stress in the aluminum layers from tensile to compressive. Subsequent tensile creep loading results in lower longitudinal stresses in the aluminum layers in the prestrained specimen than in the "as received" specimen and consequently less creep. The mechanism outlined above has been substantiated by both experimental data and an analytical model developed to predict the quasi-static and time-dependent response of ARALL-4 laminates. The demonstrated predictive capability of the analytical model provides one with a tool for optimizing the creep response of this hybrid composite by mechanical prestraining.

REFERENCES

1. Voegesang, L.B., and Gunnink, J.W., ARALL: A Material Challenge for the Next Generation of Aircraft, *Materials and Design*, Vol. 7, No. 6, Nov 86.
2. Voegesang, L.B., Chen, D., Roebroeks, G.H. and Vlot, A., "ARALL Laminates : Past, Present and Future," Proc. ARALL Laminates Users' Conference, Seven Springs, PA, October 26, 1987.
3. Voegesang, L.B., Gunnink, J.W., Chen, D., Roebroeks, G.H. and Vlot, A., "New Developments in ARALL Laminates," Proc. ARALL Laminates Technical Review Meeting, Alcoa Laboratories, Alcoa Center, PA, June 29, 1988.
4. Bucci, R.J., Mueller, L.N., Voegesang, L.B. and Gunnink, J.W., "ARALL Laminates Properties and Design Update," Proc. 33rd International SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition, Anaheim, CA, March 7-10, 1988.
5. Pindera, M-J., Williams, T.O. and Macheret, Y., "Time-Dependent Response of ARALL-4 Laminates," *Polymer Composites* (to appear in 1989).
6. Jones, R.M., *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, McGraw-Hill Book Company, New York, 1975.

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